

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF PLOT-ROLE PLAYING GAMES IN THE ACTIVITY OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. In this article, the features of development of plot-role games in the activities of preschool children, the ways of formation of children's thinking and worldview through the game are mentioned. Preschool educational organizations talk about the importance of role-playing games in helping children grow up healthy and well-rounded.

Keywords: preschool education, child, plot, role, game, character, intellectual, fairy tale, staging, toy, family.

ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ СЮЖЕТНО-РОЛЕВЫХ ИГР В ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

Аннотация. В данной статье упоминаются особенности развития сюжетно-ролевых игр в деятельности дошкольников, способы формирования детского мышления и мировоззрения посредством игры. В дошкольных образовательных организациях говорят о важности ролевых игр в воспитании детей здоровыми и всесторонне развитыми.

Ключевые слова: дошкольное образование, ребенок, сюжет, роль, игра, персонаж, интеллигент, сказка, инсценировка, игрушка, семья.

INTRODUCTION

Based on the state requirements for the development of children of primary and preschool age in our republic, there is a need to develop organizational and methodical supply for the use of plot role-playing games, the introduction of children to national culture and universal human values, and the use of various games to expand their imagination about the environment and life. Also, during the implementation of the "First Step" state educational program, it is important to develop effective methods of activities related to the formation of the moral qualities of the students based on the competence approach and the creation of the "I" concept.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the history of human being, games first entered the life of young children as a form of culture. With the help of the game, children begin to recognize objects and items without understanding their essence at first. They try to find out their location, color, sound, shape, and distinctive features. They learn, observe and remember objects, as a result of which children's worldview expands. Understanding the nature of games, understanding their educational and developmental potential for children means knowing their specific aspects and nature.

"The game is one of the means of education and recreation. It is known that a person in his life is busy with activities such as play, study, work, rest" [3]. Since the leading activity in preschool age is play, it is appropriate to use game technologies in educational activities. The game is a type of training that develops a person in every way. The game activity is combined with the study, it becomes a component of it. Therefore, most of the tasks of education are carried out with the help of games.

The creativity of a preschool child in the game is expressed in creativity, combining knowledge and imagination, expressing one's thoughts and feelings, creating a new image,

performing it in a role and bringing it to life. The development of role-playing games is related to the emergence of creative abilities in children, and these abilities develop during the game.

Z. Freud is one of the specialists who made a special contribution to game theory. He advocates two different approaches to games. Within the framework of the first approach, games are viewed as a means of satisfying needs that are impossible in social life, while the second approach shows the child's specific needs and feelings as the subject of the game. In this process, the child changes his nature and becomes active in the game [4].

L. C. Vygotsky characterized the emergence of an idea as the most important qualitative change in the genesis of a game, reflecting a fundamentally new situation between action and thought [5]. During the game, "the ability to go from thought to situation" is transformed. As a result, a new type of child's activity appears, that is, thinking moves from activity to practical activity. Represents personal and moral qualities. The role-playing game is meaningfully organized by the child's knowledge, imagination and experience. However, when creating a new idea and implementing it, the child compares it with the previously acquired knowledge. As a result, they develop the ability to dissociate, associate and combine. Children get an impression of the environment and realities, the actions of different people in society through role playing.

The game is creative processing of experienced impressions, combining them and building a new reality from them that meets the needs and desires of the child. Therefore, children have time to master TV, computer, mobile phone and other gadgets faster than adults. Today, the door of opportunities is wide open for children. For example, they can listen to the same songs together with their parents, watch the same programs on TV, visit cafes and restaurants with their family, travel abroad on vacation. We can say that they control their worldview with various famous brands, car brands and advertisements.

RESULTS

In preschool educational organizations, a special place is allocated to plot-role play in the activities of children of different ages. An important feature of the plot-role game is the presence of an imitative or completely invented situation in which the child plays the role of an adult and reproduces everything that is observed among adults, copies the work or social functions of adults, models the relationship between them. During the game, the child shows that he is in the fantasy world he wants, and he "becomes" where he wants, and participates in interesting and attractive activities in it. During the entire preschool age, the dynamics of game development goes from the first level (in junior preschool age) to the fourth level (in senior preschool age).

Children of preschool age often play alone (mutual games, individual), because they do not yet know how to communicate with each other, share roles and play materials. The theme of the games is mainly taken from everyday life: on the basis of impressions received, direct observations of the environment. These games include: "daughter and mother", "kindergarten", "car driver", "hospital treatment". An example of this is the following game.

"How can they play together?"

Purpose: to give children an understanding of team play and to strengthen their ideas about the rules of team play. Encouraging learning new rules in games and playing according to them.

Process: "Children of our group play friendly games together. Any games require its participants to follow certain rules. Because these rules help to regulate and continue the game.

He forces all the children to play games. What do you think, children, what rules should we follow in our team games?"

The teacher himself recommends the correct answers. After listening to all the answers: Congratulations, children, you said it right, with a little help from the teacher, you said the rules of the children's cooperative game correctly:

- before starting the game, think carefully with whom and what kind of game you will play and what you will need for this game;

- be sincere, polite and fair during the game; - listen to other participating children without making suggestions;

- respect those who are playing next to you, do not disturb them, do not disturb their order of play, do not take away their toys;

- learn not to go against the opinion of the majority;

- during the game it is necessary to give way, share, wait for each other and help if necessary;

- it is not possible to fight; - after the end of the game, it is necessary to put all the toys in their place.

Conclusion: Think about it, are you following these rules? (Give an example of children playing games in harmony with each other, without fighting);

Conversation 3: teaching children about friendship, kindness and the formation of moral qualities by staging a fairy tale.

DISCUSSION

When a child assumes a certain role, he rarely behaves in accordance with this role. It is difficult for children to control their emotional behavior and play an active role. At first, the game takes place only with individual appearances, but over time, a role-playing dialogue develops, and an imaginary interlocutor appears. Children who have mastered actions with plot-role play toys, freely use substitute objects in the game, can replace lost thematic toys with other objects. Gradually, the plot role-playing game changes, and as a result, it turns from a single game into a joint game with the participation of two or more children.

This transition is carried out as follows: first, the child is interested in a game on a certain topic, then he is briefly introduced to the game, and the children disperse again. However, as a result of their deep understanding of household life, children begin to understand the interaction of adults with each other and try to play this situation with their friends in the form of plot-role play. Of course, in such a case, it is necessary to organize a game that includes several roles, and discuss the progress and rules of the game with the children. In small groups, the condition for starting the game is the teacher's proposal, and in the next groups, it is based on the children's proposals. Usually, the games are short-term and last up to 10-15 minutes, in senior and preparatory groups up to 20-25 minutes. All this characterizes the level of development of the game, the main content of which is action games with objects.

CONCLUSIONS

Therefore, plot-role games show a special type of child's activity from the point of view of their internal structure, they contain a creative relationship to the surrounding reality through the mismatch of playful and real actions, which is a new creates the imagined content. The conditions of the imagined situation attract the child, make his thinking easy, open the field for

free creative activity, all this is expressed through role behavior, that is, through the actions and relationships given in the plot.

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